

Research Data Management University of Limerick Capability Maturity Report

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Introduction

This report presents the results of the evaluation of the research data management practices at the University of Limerick in January 2025. The research was conducted using the “Research Data Management Supported Self-Evaluation Instrument for Higher Education Institutes and Research Performing Organisations”.

The report contains information based on responses to questions about how the University of Limerick supports research data management through activity in three key areas of resource: Policies, Practices and Procedures; the Technological Environment and Infrastructure, and People and Human Capacity.

Each area of resource is considered in the extent to which it facilitates research data management at the various stages of the research data life cycle.

An explanation of the methodology for the research instrument is contained in the accompanying Explanatory Notes document.

Structure

The data derived from the questions are presented as follows:

1. A short statement describing the research data management provision at the institution.
2. A summary of the numerical choice for each question and a graphical representation of the frequency of the scores.
3. Graphical representations of the results for the three key areas (the Policies, Procedures and Documentation; the Technological Environment and Infrastructure and Human Capacity and Resources) arranged by the stages or phases in the research life cycle.
4. Graphical representations of the scores for the different stages in the research data life cycle by area.
5. A graphical representation of the collated results of the three key areas arranged by the stages or phases in the research life cycle.
6. Graphical representations of the results organised comparatively for the stage or phase of the research life-cycle arranged by the three key areas and for the areas ranged by the research life-cycle.
7. Tables showing the variance between the scores for the stages within each key area and between the areas within each stage.
8. A graphical representation indicates the location of the unit that determines practice in each area.

An analysis of key finding is presented, and this is supported by the contextual information provided for each question.

Section 1

Research Data Management Support at the University of Limerick

The University of Limerick supports RDM through a range of policies, infrastructural provision and staffing commitments. A RDM policy was published in 2024 and together with a suite of other relevant policies provides a framework for the practice of research data management within the university. The University provides a host of software and services to enable data management through the lifecycle. Examples include DMP online, cloud storage, the research repository (based on Figshare), the CRIS system (Pure) or a subscription to Altmetrics. The University employs a research data manager in the library to support research data management through training and consultancy.

Section 2

Table 1: Summary of the numerical choice for each question.

	Policies, Practices and Documentation	Technological Environment and Infrastructure	Human Capacity	Min	Max	Mean	Total
Fund	2	2	3	2	3	2.3	7
Plan and Design	3	2	4	2	4	3	9
Collect and Create	3	3	2	2	3	2.7	8
Analyse	3	3	2	2	3	2.7	8
Disseminate	3	4	4	4	4	3.7	11
Evaluate	2	2	2	2	2	2	6
Min	2	2	2				
Max	3	4	4				
Mean	2.7	2.7	2.8				
Total	16	16	17				

Chart 2.1 Illustrates the frequency of scores provided.

The University of Limerick shows RDM activities across the whole research life cycle and in all areas of service provision. The majority of activities can be categorized as Level 2 (Initial – Practice occurring, but happenstance, largely unplanned and reactive) and Level 3 (Managed – Intentional practice that might be lacking full exposition). In some areas UL is showing evidence of Level 4 (Defined – Proactive, documented practice, homogeneous across the organisation).

Section 3

Policies, Procedures and Documentation

Questions in this section relate to the support for research data management present in the institution's policies, procedures and documentation. This includes both specific and indirect policies that impact research data, procedures to carry and conduct processes and supporting documentation such as exemplar documents.

The answers to the questions in this section are organised along two themes; first, the presence and extent of policies, procedures and documentation. Second, the manner in which the policies, procedures and documentation are used in research data management.

Chart 3.1 depicts the level of research data management maturity for policies, procedures and documentation arranged by the six phases of the research data life cycle.

Policies and documentation at UL look mainly at the life cycle stages from plan and design to disseminate, with less consideration for funding and evaluation at the beginning and end of the life cycle. While the institutional RDM policy ensures consistency across the life cycle, the availability of underlying supporting documentation varies widely.

Technological Environment and Infrastructure

Questions in this section relate to the support for research data management present in the institution's technological infrastructure and environment. This includes Information Technology resources, the systems and general supporting environment used in research data management.

The answers to the questions in this section are organised along four themes; first, the recognition of the technological environment and infrastructure required for research data management. Second, the ability to determine the technological environment and infrastructure needs for research data management. Third, the provision of the technological environment and infrastructure for research data management. Fourth, the contribution of the technological environment and infrastructure to the practice of research data management.

Chart 3.2 depicts the level of research data management maturity for policies, procedures and documentation arranged by the six phases of the research data life-cycle.

At UL technological support for RDM at the fund, plan and design, and the evaluate phase is limited. The general support given by the Information Technology Division (ITD) for both general and specialist software and infrastructure needs has benefits for RDM in the collect and create, and analysis phase. Dissemination is supported by an institutional repository (Figshare). At the time of writing, UL is introducing a new CRIS system (Pure), which is expected to enable better capacities for impact evaluation.

Human Capacity and Resources

Questions in this section relate to the support for research data management afforded by the institution's human capacity and resources. This concerns the employment of people with the correct skills, the training and development of employees and the allocation of time for activities related to research data management.

The answers to the questions in this section are organised along four themes; first, the recognition of the skills required for research data management. Second, the employment of people with skills in research data management. Third, the provision of training for staff in research data management. Fourth, the provision of systems to account for the work required for research data management.

Chart 3.3 depicts the level of research data management maturity for policies, procedures and documentation arranged by the six phases of the research data life-cycle.

RDM support provided by the UL library focuses on the plan and design, and on the disseminate phase of the research life cycle as these require less discipline specific expertise as the collect and create or analysis phase.

Section 4

The charts in this section present the answers by the stages of the research data lifecycle. For the purposes of this study, the research data life cycle is understood to have six phases: Fund, Plan and Design, Collect and Create, Analyse, Disseminate and Evaluate.

Fund

The *fund* stage of the research involves preparing funding applications and securing appropriate financial resources to conduct and complete the research. For the purposes of this study, it involves ensuring that research data management is adequately addressed in funding applications and decision making.

Plan and Design

The *plan and design* phase of research involves the preparatory stages of research. In terms of research data management, it will involve tasks such preparing a data management plan, planning how data will be stored, ensuring the appropriate technological systems are in place to facilitate data management and ensuring appropriate staff are in place to facilitate research data management and that training is in place for them.

Collect and Create

The *collect and create* phase of the research lifecycle involves gathering and generating data or materials to address research questions. This phase includes designing and running experiments, conducting surveys, interviews or observations and collecting and producing primary or secondary data. It may also involve creating new datasets, prototypes, models or works of art.

Analyse

The *analyse* phase of the research lifecycle focuses on interpreting and making sense of collected data to answer research questions or test hypotheses. This phase involves applying statistical, qualitative, or computational methods to identify patterns, trends, and relationships and interpretative techniques to develop understanding. Researchers use tools such as software, coding frameworks, or theoretical models to derive insights. Critical evaluation ensures data validity, reliability and generalisability and address limitations or bias.

Disseminate

The *disseminate* phase of the research lifecycle involves sharing research findings and research data with relevant audiences to maximize their impact. This phase includes publishing results in academic monographs and edited collections, academic journals, presenting at conferences, creating reports and / or using media platforms like broadcast media such as radio and television programs, websites, podcasts or social media and making

research data produced in the conduct of research available through appropriate channels such as data repositories.

Evaluate

The *evaluate* phase of the research life cycle involves assessing the quality, impact, and effectiveness of the research process and outcomes. Researchers critically review methodologies, data integrity, and conclusions to ensure validity and reliability. This phase includes peer-review, feedback from stakeholders, and analysing metrics such as citations, societal impact or policy influence.

The charts illustrate how the answers for each stage differentiated by the area.

Chart 4.1 depicts the level of research data management maturity for the fund stage of research arranged by the areas of research.

Through the research office and the library UL supports researchers to meet RDM requirements in funding applications through information sessions and consultancy. While a recurring activity, it is not well defined or documented.

Chart 4.2 depicts the level of research data management maturity for the plan and design stage of research arranged by the areas of research.

Support for plan and design (mainly to meet funder requirements for data management plans) is provided by the library through consultation and training. Both activities rely on little technological support at this point.

Chart 4.3 depicts the level of research data management maturity for the collect and create stage of research arranged by the areas of research.

ITD provides infrastructure like cloud storage and both general and specialist software that is utilised for RDM by researchers in both the collect and create, and the analyse phase of the research life cycle. The highly specific discipline and method requirements are reflected in the number of particular policies, documentations and guidelines utilised by UL.

Chart 4.4 depicts the level of research data management maturity for the analyse stage of research arranged by the areas of research.

Chart 4.5 depicts the level of research data management maturity for the disseminate stage of research arranged by the areas of research.

The UL library provides a well-supported institutional repository based on Figshare. A new repository policy supporting this is currently being drafted.

Chart 4.6 depicts the level of research data management maturity for the evaluate stage of research arranged by the areas of research.

So far, evaluation of impact at UL has focused on research publications, but not datasets, but the introduction of a new CRIS system (Pure) and further and deeper engagement with existing subscription service Altmetrics can enable deeper engagement.

Section 5

Chart 5.1 is a graphical representation of the combined results of the three key areas arranged by the stages or phases in the research life cycle.

Overall, the plan and design and the disseminate phase of the research life cycle are best supported at UL.

Chart 5.2 is a graphical representation of the collated result of the stages by the areas.

The collated results show an even distribution across the areas.

Section 6

Chart 6.1 is a graphical representation of the comparative results of the three key areas arranged by the stages or phases in the research life cycle. The chart depicts the differences between areas by the stages.

While chart 5.2 indicates that when averaged there is a general similarity in scores, chart 6.1 shows the heterogeneity of the scores across the different stages.

Chart 6.2 is a graphical representation of the comparative results of the phases in the research life cycle arranged by the key areas.

While the three areas have a similar score on average (16, 16 and 17) chart 6.2 shows consistency across the policy and documentation area, but distinct strengths and weaknesses within technological environment and infrastructure, and human capacity.

Section 7

Calculations of the variance between the collated scores for the stages within each key area and between the collated scores for each area within each research phase.

The below table details the variance in the scores for each area. The higher the score, the greater the heterogeneity between the different phases of the research data life cycle within the area.

Table 2

	Policies, Practices and Documentation	Technological Environment and Infrastructure	Human Capacity
Variance	0.14	0.56	0.81

There is very little variety in the scores for policy, practices and documentation, more for the technological environment and infrastructure and human capacity having a much higher score. This does not indicate the level of provision within an area of interest but does indicate that human capacity is far more mixed in its support and facilitation of RDM across the research life cycle while the scores for policies, practices and documentation are remarkably consistent.

The below table details the variance within the three areas by the phases of research.

Table 3

	Fund	Plan and Design	Collect and Create	Analyse	Disseminate	Evaluate
Variance	0.22	0.67	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22

Plan and design is considerably more varied than the other stages.

Section 8

Graphical representations of the responses to the supplementary question concerning the location of the responsible unit for each area and stage of the research life cycle. Multiple answers are possible - a topic may be impacted by policies from the Research Group, the Department, central units in the university and / or an external organisation.

Chart 8.1 a graphical representation of the summary of unit that determines practice by area.

Policies are set primarily at the institution level but supplemented at the departmental and from external bodies. This reflects the practice of discipline specific practices located in departmental processes supported by more general institutional policies that afford adherence to wider legislation and best practice.

For infrastructure and environment again institutional level activity is the largest recorded area with research groups and external bodies also figuring. The general provision by central ITD is supplemented by individual solutions in the research groups and specialist services from third parties.

For human capacity, the scores were restricted to institutional level and research group activity.

Chart 8.2 a graphical representation of the summary of unit that determines practice by stage.

Both the collect and create, analyse and to a lesser extent the fund phases tend to be discipline specific and accordingly these stages are impacted by research groups, departments and external bodies in addition to university level policies.

Analysis

Overall

The University of Limerick (UL) has **activity occurring in all the areas** covered in the research instrument. As shown in chart 2.1, of the 18 areas investigated it has 8 scores at level 2, 7 at level 3, and 3 at level 4. The lowest score being a 2 and the highest being 4.

Highest and lowest scoring stage

UL currently scores highest in its research data support at the disseminate stage of research particularly within the technological environment and infrastructure and in human capacity. The contextual information indicates that this strength lies in the support offered by the library through the employment of a Research Data Management specialist – “Key staff are located in the Library” and, as noted in the initial description, through its provision of specialist software.

The second most well supported stage of the research life cycle is plan and design. The presence of a specialist staff member to assist in the development of research data management plan contributes to this score.

The presence of an RDM specialist is further evident in the planning and design score for human capacity.

The **lowest scoring** stages are **fund** and **evaluate** though neither scores highly in variance – this indicates that scores are low across all areas; policies, technical infrastructure and human capacity. There is no section that is comparatively weak or strong.

Highest and lowest scoring area

As table 1 and chart 5.2 indicate the combined scores for the three areas are very similar at 16, for both the policies, procedures and documentation and the technological environment and infrastructure and 17 for human capacity.

Variance

The variance scores noted in table 2 indicate that the policies, procedures and documentation is the most homogeneous in support of the different stages of the research lifecycle while human capacity is the most heterogeneous. The high variance score in human capacity coupled with the comparatively high scores for plan and design and disseminate (charts 3.3 and 5.1) indicate that there are clear areas of intrinsically identifiable good practice with other areas scoring less well.

Location of units that determine practice.

The majority of practice is determined by units located at the institution level such as the library, IT division and the research office. It is worth noting that research groups and external bodies do have impact, though this occurs in slightly different ways. As shown in chart 8.1 research groups tend to impact the technical infrastructure and environment and the human capacity while external bodies impact the policies, procedure and documentation and technical environment and infrastructure.

Conclusion

The University of Limerick offers research data management support at some level across all areas of the research data lifecycle. The level of this support is heterogeneous across the stages. There is overall consistency in provision across the three different areas although this overall figures masks heterogeneity within the areas.

It is advised that the findings of this report be considered in terms of the University of Limerick's business plans and overall strategic aims.